

SUM OF POWERS OF NATURAL NUMBERS USING
GENERATING FUNCTION

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Abstract:

Sum of powers of Natural numbers could be determined using various techniques and these techniques have fascinated mathematicians across the globe since ancient times. In this paper we are going to present one technique of determining sum of powers of natural numbers using a generating function defined explicitly. Some new formulas were established and using them, we have explained how to evaluate the sum of powers of natural numbers.

Key Words: Sum of k^{th} Powers of Natural Numbers, Generating Function, Principle of Mathematical Induction, Fundamental Theorem of Calculus

1. Definition:

Let us denote the sum of k^{th} powers of first n natural numbers by

$$S_k(n) = 1^k + 2^k + \dots + n^k \tag{1}$$

We notice that, $S_0(n) = n$

2. Definition of Generating Function $G_{m+1}(x)$:

Let us define the generating function $G_{m+1}(x)$ for $m \geq 0$ as follows:

$$G_{m+1}(x) = (m + 1) \left[\int_0^x G_m(t) dt - x \int_0^1 G_m(t) dt \right] + x \tag{2}$$

$$G_0(x) = x$$

3. Evaluation of $G_{m+1}(x)$ for $m = 0, 1, 2, 3$:

In view of formulas presented in [1], we know that $S_k(n)$ is a polynomial in n of degree $k + 1$.

From (2), we notice that for $m = 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} G_1(x) &= \left[\int_0^x G_0(t) dt - x \int_0^1 G_0(t) dt \right] + x \\ &= \int_0^x t dt - x \int_0^1 t dt + x = \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x}{2} \\ &= 1 + 2 + \dots + x \\ \text{Thus, } G_1(x) &= S_1(x) \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Similarly from (2), we notice that for $m = 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} G_2(x) &= 2 \left[\int_0^x G_1(t) dt - x \int_0^1 G_1(t) dt \right] + x \\ &= 2 \left[\frac{1}{2} \int_0^x (t^2 + t) dt - \frac{x}{2} \int_0^1 (t^2 + t) dt \right] + x \\ &= \frac{x^3}{3} + \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x}{6} \\ &= 1^2 + 2^2 + 3^2 + \dots + x^2 \\ \text{Thus, } G_2(x) &= S_2(x) \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

From (2), we notice that for $m = 2$,

$$\begin{aligned} G_3(x) &= 3 \left[\int_0^x G_2(t) dt - x \int_0^1 G_2(t) dt \right] + x \\ &= 3 \left[\int_0^x \left(\frac{t^3}{3} + \frac{t^2}{2} + \frac{t}{6} \right) dt - x \int_0^1 \left(\frac{t^3}{3} + \frac{t^2}{2} + \frac{t}{6} \right) dt \right] + x \\ &= \frac{x^4}{4} + \frac{x^3}{2} + \frac{x^2}{4} \\ &= 1^3 + 2^3 + 3^3 + \dots + x^3 \\ \text{Thus, } G_3(x) &= S_3(x) \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

For $m = 3$, from (2), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} G_4(x) &= 4 \left[\int_0^x G_3(t) dt - x \int_0^1 G_3(t) dt \right] + x \\ &= 4 \left[\int_0^x \left(\frac{t^4}{4} + \frac{t^3}{2} + \frac{t^2}{4} \right) dt - x \int_0^1 \left(\frac{t^4}{4} + \frac{t^3}{2} + \frac{t^2}{4} \right) dt \right] + x \\ &= \frac{x^5}{5} + \frac{x^4}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} - \frac{x}{30} \\ &= 1^4 + 2^4 + 3^4 + \dots + x^4 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $G_4(x) = S_4(x)$ (6)

We now prove a result regarding generating function $G_m(x + 1)$

4. Theorem 1:

For $m \geq 0$, we have $G_m(x + 1) = G_m(x) + (x + 1)^m$ (7), where $G_m(0) = 0$

Proof:

We prove (7) by mathematical induction on m .

Let $m = 0$. Then by (2), we have $G_0(x + 1) = x + 1$

Also, $G_0(x) + (x + 1)^0 = x + 1$.

Hence (7) is true if $m = 0$.

Let $m = 1$. Then using (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} G_1(x + 1) &= \int_0^{x+1} G_0(t) dt - (x + 1) \int_0^1 G_0(t) dt + (x + 1) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot (x + 1)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (x + 1) = \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{3x}{2} + 1 \\ G_1(x) + (x + 1)^1 &= \int_0^x G_0(t) dt - x \int_0^1 G_0(t) dt + x + x + 1 \\ &= \frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{x}{2} + 2x + 1 = \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{3x}{2} + 1 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, (7) is also true for $m = 1$.

Hence by induction hypothesis, assume that (7) is true up to m and we will prove for $m + 1$.

i.e., Let us assume that $G_k(x + 1) = G_k(x) + (x + 1)^k$ (8), for all $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Let us prove the statement is true for $k = m + 1$.

That is, we will prove that $G_{m+1}(x + 1) = G_{m+1}(x) + (x + 1)^{m+1}$ (9)

Now using (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} &G_{m+1}(x + 1) - G_{m+1}(x) \\ &= (m + 1) \left[\int_0^{x+1} G_m(t) dt - (x + 1) \int_0^1 G_m(t) dt \right] + x + 1 \\ &\quad - \left\{ (m + 1) \left[\int_0^x G_m(t) dt - x \int_0^1 G_m(t) dt \right] + x \right\} \\ &= (m + 1) \int_0^x G_m(t) dt + (m + 1) \int_x^{x+1} G_m(t) dt - x(m + 1) \int_0^1 G_m(t) dt \\ &\quad - (m + 1) \int_0^1 G_m(t) dt + x + 1 - (m + 1) \int_0^x G_m(t) dt + x(m + 1) \int_0^1 G_m(t) dt - x \\ &= (m + 1) \int_x^{x+1} G_m(t) dt - (m + 1) \int_0^1 G_m(t) dt + 1 \end{aligned}$$

Differentiating with respect to x on both sides, and using Fundamental theorem of calculus, and equation (8), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dx} \{G_{m+1}(x + 1) - G_{m+1}(x)\} &= (m + 1)G_m(x + 1) - (m + 1)G_m(x) \\ &= (m + 1)(x + 1)^m \end{aligned}$$

Integrating with respect to x on both sides,

$$G_{m+1}(x + 1) - G_{m+1}(x) = (x + 1)^{m+1} + C \tag{10}$$

To find the value of C, let us put $x = 0$ in (10)

$$G_{m+1}(1) - G_{m+1}(0) = 1 + C \tag{11}$$

Now let us find the values of $G_{m+1}(1), G_{m+1}(0)$ using (2).

$$\begin{aligned} G_{m+1}(1) &= (m + 1) \left[\int_0^1 G_m(t) dt - \int_0^1 G_m(t) dt \right] + 1 = 1 \\ G_{m+1}(0) &= (m + 1) \left[\int_0^0 G_m(t) dt - 0 \cdot \int_0^1 G_m(t) dt \right] + 0 = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Substituting these values in (11), $1 = 1 + C$ giving $C = 0$.

Hence (10) becomes,

$$G_{m+1}(x + 1) - G_{m+1}(x) = (x + 1)^{m+1}. \text{ This proves (9).}$$

Hence by Principle of Mathematical Induction, (7) holds true for all values of m , such that $m \geq 0$

This completes the proof.

Now, we prove an important relation between $G_m(n)$ and $S_m(n)$.

5. Theorem 2:

For any two natural numbers n and m , $G_m(n) = S_m(n)$ (12)

Proof:

Let us prove (12) using induction on n .

We notice from (2), that for $n = 1$,

$$G_m(1) = m \left[\int_0^1 G_{m-1}(t) dt - \int_0^1 G_{m-1}(t) dt \right] + 1 = 1 \text{ and from (1), we obtain}$$

$$S_m(1) = 1^m = 1. \text{ Hence, } G_m(1) = S_m(1). \text{ So (12) is true if } n = 1.$$

By Induction Hypothesis, let us assume that (12) is true up to $n = k$ and we will prove (12) for $n = k + 1$.

$$\text{i.e, } G_m(n) = S_m(n) = 1^m + 2^m + \dots + n^m \text{ for } n = 1, 2, \dots, k \quad (13)$$

Using (13) and (7) of theorem 1, for $n = k + 1$, we obtain

$$S_m(k+1) = 1^m + 2^m + \dots + k^m + (k+1)^m = G_m(k) + (k+1)^m = G_m(k+1)$$

Thus, (12) is true for $n = k + 1$ also if it is true up to $n = k$.

Hence by Principle of Mathematical Induction, (12) is true, for all natural numbers n and m .

This completes the proof.

5. Conclusion

In this paper we have defined a generating function namely $G_{m+1}(x)$ recursively as in (2). Using this, in (7) of theorem 1, we have proved a relationship for G between successive values $x + 1$ and x . Now using this result, we have established a nice relation between the generating and summation function that $G_m(n) = S_m(n)$. Thus, we may obtain sum of powers of natural numbers using the generating function described here in quite easier way than the usual laborious process. This is computationally convenient since, to determine sum up to m th powers of natural numbers, it is enough to just know the sum of first $(m - 1)$ th powers of natural numbers. Equations (3), (4), (5), (6) of section 3, provide a justification of the general result (12) obtained in theorem 2. Thus theorem 2 provides a new insight for computing sum of powers of natural numbers among several existing methods.

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